

Research

Self-Defense Legislations, Yesterday, Today and Tomorrow: A Study from Afghanistan Perspective

Mahfuz Ullah Arify^{1*}, Mohammad Aimal Haqmal², Ahmad Gul Wasiq³

¹Assistant Professor, Faculty of Law and Political Science, Department of Public Law Nangarhar University, Afghanistan

²Associate Professor, Faculty of Law and Political Science, Department of Public Law Nangarhar University, Afghanistan

³Professor, Faculty of Law and Political Science, Department of Public Law Nangarhar University, Afghanistan

***Corresponding author**

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Abstract : The legal system of Afghanistan contains Islamic, Statutory and customary rules. It has developed over centuries and is presently varying in the context of the rebuilding of the Afghanistan. The supreme law of Afghanistan is the Constitution of Afghanistan. Furthermore, there is composite of legislation which stems from different historical eras. The so-called four volumes of civil law were formulated on the basis of Egyptian models and promulgated in the time of the monarchy. Other legislation came into force under of President Daoud Khan, the Democratic Republic (1978-1992), the Mujahideen (1992-1996), the Taliban regime (1996-2001) and the existing Islamic Republic of Afghanistan. Article 130 of the Afghanistan Constitution establishes that judges must apply the constitution and legislation and may only resort to Hanafi Fiqh (one of the Schools of Islamic Law) if a essential legal rule cannot be found in the written laws. According to the Afghan law system, administration of justice, accused is presumed to be innocent till proved guilty. In such conditions, it is load upon prosecution to prove its case against the accused. But in certain circumstances, the weight of proving guilt of the accused move towards accused and the law makes the accused responsible to prove his innocence. This kind of condition ascends when accused after commission of crime taken a ground as a defense for the unlawful act done. It is named plea of defense. There are numerous bases existing to the accused in Afghanistan Penal Code (1925, 1975, and 2017). The Afghanistan Apex Courts while identifying the plea of Self-Defense delivered specific guide lines for the trial courts so as to evade any error of judgments since it is the central principle of administration of justice that accused should not be convicted if there is a miniature doubt on amount of the prosecution. In this article we will use the various judgments of the superior courts so as to grasp on a final conclusion that how accused can take advantage of the plea of self-defense and in what conditions the choice of self-defense cannot be look into contemplation.

Keywords: *Afghanistan Penal Code, Criminal Law, Self-Defense, and Supreme Court of Afghanistan.*

Introduction

The inadequate practical value of Afghanistan's statutory law cannot be attributed merely to the decay and ultimate demise of a dominant political authority in Afghanistan as a result both of more than twenty years of civil war and the sway of the Taliban. Weinbaum (1980), found that even 'where recognized statutes exist, judges usually dearth the training and research resources essential to recognize suitable provisions of the law.' He also documented that 'several are also comprehensibly overwhelmed by the necessity to adjust positive law, often foreign in origin, to the Afghan experience.' The excruciating of the legal system into formal law and informal law has been a hallmark of Afghan legal history ever since endeavors were made to present statutory laws. In fact, it is possible to go advance and state with some confidence that past experience would recommend that any attempt to apply and enforce secular statutory laws which depart from customary and/or particular interpretations of Islamic law is liable to be met with gripes and perhaps even civil strife (Amin, 2015).

All current laws are pertinent unless they are in defilement of the 1964 Constitution, international legal obligations or the Bonn Agreement. Significant changes to the law were introduced due to political changes in the late 1970s and are replicated in the Law of Criminal Procedure. While the Criminal Procedure Law of May 1965, as revised in 1974, provided that imprisonment of a suspect on whatsoever grounds cannot surpass one week unless authorized by a court (see articles 26, 28, and 29), this condition altered profoundly in 1981. The Law on the Discovery and Investigation of Crimes and Supervision of the Attorney General on Its Legal Enforcement of March 1979, as revised in 1981, permitted the Attorney General more broader powers including the power to impede a suspect for up to 6 months without any court sanction being obligatory. It is not specific which of the 2 provisions govern at least in theory the imprisonment time of suspects in criminal investigations. The similar degree of legal uncertainty relates to other parts of law that experienced changes as a result of political transformations. Most protuberant are the land reforms laws, which were presented after the coup of April 1978: it has been impossible to create the fate of these laws or the current status of any measures taken under them (Amin, 2015).

A vigilant investigation of the statutory structure of Afghanistan's legal system is therefore fraught with both practical and theoretical complications. On a practical level, it is uncertain whether any broader propagation of current laws would result in an improvement of the rule of law or human rights. Secondly, the corpus of statutory laws offers itself in layers, each layer demonstrating specific periods of governance. It is mainly a political task to decide which of these layers should be applied, if at all. The redeployment of laws from a specific time cannot therefore be considered as a politically neutral exercise since it levies on the current courts and institutes a specific choice of laws. Statutory laws were endorsed under the Constitutions of Afghanistan of 1964, 1977, 1980, 1987, 1990 and 1992 (Khan & Hamid, 2015). During these eras of constitutional rule new statutes were ratified and present ones revised or superseded. Thus, it is likely to be regarded controversial which laws should now be documented as valid and enforceable.

Afghanistan Constitution

The 1964 Constitution of Afghanistan was the constitution of Afghanistan with the main objective to prepare the government and the masses for steady crusade towards democracy and socio-economic transformation. A Loya Jirgah (grand council of notables) had debated, revised and accepted its innovations, which comprised a bill of rights for all Afghans, explicitly comprising women. After public evaluation the constitution was put to applicable in October 1964 (International Legal Foundation, 2004).

Criminal Law in Afghanistan

Essential criminal law in Afghanistan lasts to be governed in big part by Islamic law. The first complete codification was ratified as the Penal Code of 1925. This was followed by the Criminal Law of September 1976. It seems that the Criminal Law of 1976 presents a quasi-secular system for all *tazir* offences i.e. offences which appeal under Islamic criminal law only discretionary punishments administered by the state - but holds the system of Islamic *hadd* punishments, reprisal and payment of fines for 'Islamic' crimes, which are to be penalized according to the principles of the Hanafi school of Islam. Contingent on the nature of the proof available against an accused, *hadd* punishments will be levied on those who have been found guilty of theft, road theft, infidelity, rape and fornication (Khan, Hamid, 2015).

Some of the punishments awarded for hadd offences, such as, the pelting to death of an adulterer if specific evidential necessities are met, do conflict with both the 1964 Constitution, which prohibits the hassle of punishments ‘unharmonious with humanoid dignity’ (Article 31) and Afghanistan’s international legal obligations. Apart from Islamic penalties, the residual provisions of the Criminal Law of 1976 are modeled on European principles of criminal law and are thus inconspicuous. It is in the extent of Islamic punishments that the most blatant conflicts with international human rights standards exist. This is also the field of law that is likely to be the most complex to reform.

The question of reform of these facets of Afghanistan’s criminal law has to be assumed as founding portion of 2 inquiries both related but nevertheless different. Firstly, the Criminal Law of 1976, such as it is, is not broadly practical or enforced. In exercise almost all courts, comprising the Supreme Court of Afghanistan depends on Islamic law directly. It is basically a political question whether or not this condition should last to exist and a applied question whether or not it would be possible, even if regarded as desirable, to change the de facto law of the land. Secondly, any official obligation to the implementation of a codified criminal law, be it in the form of a new law or through the re-enactment or dissemination of the prevailing law of 1976, would involve as of requirement the prerequisite to deal with Islamic penalties either eliminating them or de facto affirming them. Both situations are difficult courses of action. Any catastrophe to detachment itself from the drastic elucidation and ruthless imposition of their specific brand of Islamic law by the Taliban will bring the Government into conflict with the intercontinental community and the evolving human rights community of Afghanistan. However, any essential project to eradicate Islamic penalties, and thus crimes, from the statute book is liable to be assumed contentious by the massive of the population.

The Elements that Constitute a Crime in Afghan Criminal Law

According to Criminal Law of Afghanistan (2017), the legal components of crime in both theory and practice a person cannot be found guilty of a crime if the crime is not shielded by the law or by Islamic law. The meaning of the legal component in Afghan criminal law is that the legal component of crime designates the crime and the penalty. The utmost imperative component of a criminal office is that it is recognized as a crime in the law. The third component in Afghan criminal law is the belief that: “no person can be penalized contrary to the components

of a law which was not in effective afore the commission of the crime.” According to the Article 21 of criminal law: “A person who commits a crime when a law is effective can be punished. If a new law is introduced before the final judgment of the court and the judgment is a sentence, the newest law will be the applicable law, otherwise the new law will be the active law.” According to Afghanistan criminal law there are certain situations under which the person committing a crime will not be penalized. These are called equal conditions. The presence of these settings makes lawful what otherwise would have constituted a crime. The exoneration condition divides into three conditions:

1. Using one’s right to obtain one’s rights,
2. Legitimate self-defense and
3. Acting on duty.

According to Article 53 of the criminal law: “Commission of a crime for personal welfare or exercise of one’s own rights is guaranteed to all persons by Islamic and written law.” According to Article 55 of the criminal law: “Commission of a crime while on government duty, according to the components of the law, is not a crime.” According to Article 57 of the criminal law: “Commission of a crime to attain one’s own rights is not a crime.”

Elements of a Crime

Crime is classified into pre-determined crimes and non-determined crimes. In pre-determined crimes both intention and determination are the objective of criminal. There is a discrepancy between motive and intention; the motive occasionally generates crimes but sometimes even if a person knows that his act is a crime, there will be no penalty for the crime. Examples are self-defense and using one’s rights. All the prior is enshrined in the law, but in the provinces of Afghanistan, and sometimes even in the cities, in practice people respect tradition and custom.

Self-Defense

Murray and Louis, (2006) documented that right of self-defense would ascend where risk to individual or property is imminent and would endure available as long as such risk exists. Right of self-defense can be deployed as a protection toward off an unwarranted attack to individual or property but it cannot be used as a vehicle for provoking the attack, meaning

thereby that it is to be exercised as defensive measure and not for initiation attack. When definite plea of self-defense is elevated, the onus to prove the same lay upon the party appealing the same. Such right would encompass only when a clear danger to person or property become looming, and the instant he surpasses such right then that act become the act of aggression.

Self-defense justifies an otherwise illegal act and works along the same lines as an inevitability claim, which we will discuss further in the following segment. In fact, it may help to think about self-defense as a kind of need defense. Like necessity, self-defense is an explanatory defense. When otherwise illegal conduct is confirmed to be assumed in a lawful act of self-defense, the Penal Code assumes that conduct lawful.

Although the resemblances between necessity and self-defense, it is worth investigative the exact characteristics of self-defense claims under the Penal Code of Afghanistan. According to Article 57 of the Penal Code, an otherwise criminal act will not subject one to criminal liability if the defendant has a lawful genuine defense. When a police officer or other authorized government official cannot defend a person who is in risk, that individual has the right and even the duty to defend him as well as others in an alike condition. Article 58 more defines the strictures of self-defense by elucidating the law “permits the endangered person to use of any essential method for the aim of defending against any criminal action that possesses a substantial loss or hazard of life to the defender or somebody else.” Articles 57 through 64 of the Penal Code discuss self-defense. Article 57 states the fundamental statement: “commitment of a criminal action for the aim of exercising the valid right of defense shall not be considered a crime.” After all, it seems ridiculous to penalize an individual for protecting himself/herself from an assailant. Still, not all claims of self-defense are lawful. Article states: the “legitimate right of defense came into existence when the defender is assured by rational instruments and logical causes that a threat of misdemeanor is absorbed to property, life, or honor of the defender or somebody else.” It is significant to note that an individual may raise self-defense about actions defending himself or other. Building on the rule outlined in Article 59, Article 60 elucidates the elements essential for a rigorous claim of self-defense.

Penal Code of Afghanistan – Article 60

The Penal Code of Afghanistan, article 60 describes that defense must be;

- Against hostility and attacks;

- Against proportionate to the hazard;
- The only way of confiscating the threat;
- Contemporaneous with the attack of the other side;
- Against an unlawful and unfair action;
- The defender should not have intentionally caused the criminal act of the other side.

Additional limits on legal self-defense entitlements identify the state's exclusive part in offering for public safety. For example, self-defense is not a lawful claim when it is possible to get defense from public officials (Article 62). Likewise, self-defense does not validate the use of power against public officials "who perform their duties in decent intent, even if in the course of duty they go afar the boundaries of their lawful power," excluding where a logical dread of death or stern damage occurs (Article 63). The rationale behind these provisions is that extensive disorder could effect if people regularly employ power against state officials. A self-defense claim might also effect the court's condemning. Self-defense can function as a diminishing factor even if the defendant's conduct does not meet all of the requirements of a lawful claim under Article 60 of the Penal Code. This generally happens when a criminal action begin out as an action of self-defense, but intensifies into a full on criminal action because the defendant uses very much power to defend himself/herself. Article 64 awards judge the power to decrease the punishment of somebody who, in good faith, employs very much strength in defense of himself or another.

The Law of Self Defense – A Case

Suppose Sahil is walking to the marketplace when he is confronted by Zia. Zia takes out a blade, forces Sahil into an alley, and ask money. Sahil pulls out a gun and shoots Zia. The gunshot kills him. Is this a lawful case of self-defense? Most likely, so long as possession of the weapon is lawful. Sahil is a guiltless victim of a stern, gratuitous violent attack, and there is no way to plausibly escape. Sahil does not have a firearm. Instead, he wrestles the blade away from Zia and then stabs him to death. Is this a lawful case of self-defense under the Penal Code? Perhaps, Sahil clearly was under deadly attack, but since Sahil now has the blade, it is at least arguable that he could have safely retreated or that the force employed was extreme. On the other hand, Sahil could have reasonably settled given the conditions that Zia would continue the

pursuit, possibly even with another deadly weapon, unless Sahil stopped him (Richard, Singer, John., Fond, 2007).

According to codified law a person right under this heading continues unless the hazard or apprehension of being in danger continuous.

Exceptions to the Right of Self-Defense (Statutory Provisions)

(a) Acts against which there is no Right of Self Defense. There is no right of self-defense against an action which does not reasonably as the anxiety of death of grievous hurt done by public servant in good faith. Directing by public servant in good faith. When person has time to have recourse to the public authorities. It cannot extend to perpetrating more impairment than is essential to inflict.”

(b)When Right of Self Defense of Body Extend to Cause Death. The right of body extends, under the limitations stated in the statute, to voluntary instigating death or any other damage to attacker provided if, there is anxiety of death from attack. Anxiety of grievous hurt. Purpose of doing rape. Purpose of doing un-natural desire. Purpose of kidnapping or snatching. Purpose of wrongfully restraining an individual, when he detains that he is incapable to recourse to public authorities for his release.”

(c)When Right of Self Defense of Property Extend to Causing Death. The right of self-defense prolongs under constraint, to voluntary causing death or any other damage provided if, there is anxiety of theft. Anxiety of home-breaking by dark. Damage by fire committed on any lodging place. Robbery, injury or home trespass and hazard of death or grievous hurt.

Application of Right of Self Defense

Self-defense is a Countermeasure that includes defending oneself, one's Property, or the well-being of another from Harm. The usage of the Right of self-defense as a lawful justification for the usage of power in times of risk is available in several Jurisdictions, but the clarification differs extensively. Such right was given by majority of nations of the globe in same way to defend and endorsed fairness and justice in the society, with deliberation to reinforce the wellbeing of the masses to applying lucid awareness in problematic condition to defend their lives and stuff form attack of the criminal subject to certain constraints that the law levies.

General Limitations on Right of Self Defense

Right of self-defense was continuously exposed to overall confines, levied by Panel Code of Afghanistan. Right of self-defense was available if the government official had acted in good faith and under color of his office. Right of self-defense was to be employed as a protection to ward off on warranted attack to an individual or goods, but it could not be employed as vehicle for infuriating an attack. Right of self-defense was to be applied as a defensive measure and not for initiation an attack for reactive purpose. Court would have to scrutinize such queries with reference to the realities of all circumstance and keeping in view the state of mind of the individual placed in the position of the individual attacked who exercised the right of self-defense. Encounter would not enable a police party to kill indiscriminately the individuals who were supposedly involved in the encounter as the fundamental requirement given in Panel Code of Afghanistan.

Right of Self Defense Extending to Causing Death

Applicability, Contention of the prosecution was that even if it was admitted that the accused and co-accused had acted in self-defense, it was obvious on track that they had surpassed such defense by taking the life of the dead. Validity, Defense side had categorically contended that the dead and the hurt prosecution witness were armed, therefore, despite disarming of the said hurt witness by the co-accused, there still remained an anxiety of looming threat of death or grievous injure from the armed-deceased to the accused and co- accused, Finishing that the accused and co-accused had surpassed the right of self- defense, in conditions, would not be reasonable. Medico-legal report of the accused specified that he had sustained five firearm wounds, but said report had been willfully suppressed by the prosecution in the first inquiry report. Which cast stern doubt in the prosecution story and rendered the testimony of the accuser devoid of intrinsic worth and inherent worth? Existence of the accused at the time and place of incidence, in situations, became extremely doubtful; therefore he could not be securely trusted upon. Co-accused was admittedly seventy (70) years of age at the time of the alleged incidence and no explicit action had been' endorsed to him excluding his meager existence at the time and place of incidence, hence, his untrue insinuation could not be ruled out. No intention was alleged against the dead and the hurt tribunal witness. No provision of the material witness against whom the intention was principally alleged by the accuser also made the prosecution

version doubtful. Trial Court had accurately settled that the defense plea seemed to be plausible and convincing in all fairness of the facts and conditions of the case and that the prosecution had failed to bring the guiltiness of the suspected and co-suspected home beyond any sound doubt. Appeal against acquittal was dismissed, in circumstances.

Exercise and Extent of Right of Self Defense

Once an occasion of the exercise of the right of self-defense has risen, the suspect cannot be likely to control the degree of power to be used by him to keep his act within the restrictions given by the law and therefore, the law grants certain minimal latitude to the accused. Where the power used is grossly out of fraction to the danger occasioned by the assailant or the force used after the threat is over that the law ponders such power to be in excess of the right of self-defense and levies punishments.

Preconditions for Right of Self-Defense

Such right can be prolonged not only to defense of one's own body against any crime impacting human body but can also be drawn-out defending body of any other person. If suspect wants to take advantage of exclusion of right of self-defense, then he must show that he was not accountable or at fault or on account of his act the incidence occurred; that fairly assumed that his life was under abrupt threat; that also supposed that there was no realistic source available to escape or evade need; and that had no purpose to cause more injury than essential for the purpose. Whenever there is quarrel between person, it is indispensable to determine as to which person was attacker. Once it is obviously recognized that one of the person begun the attack, the other person would have a right to self-defense.

Burden of Proof in Cases of Self-Defense

Afore appealing the right of self-defense, burden of proof is continuously on prosecution and it is only when a good prima facie case has been made out against accused adequate to vindicate his verdict for that offence, then burden moves upon the accused to evident that he is not guilty of some crime. For that suspect must set forth the meticulous conditions in which he acted that he was correct in what he did. Such move of burden upon suspect is not parallel to that of prosecution to create the case beyond reasonable doubt but the test as to whether accused was

entitled to the benefit of right of self-defense is not whether he has proved the case beyond a reasonable doubt but whether in setting up any defense he has established a rational doubt in the case of prosecution and thereby earned his right of exoneration that can be done either leading proof or through cross- investigation of witnesses or from the prosecution proof itself. Even then whole proof is to be looked into and upon contemplation of such proof it is to be perceived as to whether or not an adequate doubt is produced in the mind of the Court that accused is entitled to the benefit of self-defense; upon answer of such question, plea of accused should be decided.

Conduct of the Accused in such Cases

Principles are that conduct of the accused during the entire matter and his existence at the spot must be bona fide, impeccable and devoid of elements of mens rea or actus reus; that there must be a threat to the life of the suspect or of grievous bodily injury or a real anxiety to that impact, that the condition must be such that the accused is left with no choice of a anodyne exit; and that the power used by the accused is proportional to the apprehended danger. Credible proof or situations to designate that initiating of death was essential to protect the life of the accused are to be exist in case of murder.

Plea of Self-Defense has to be taken at Early Stage of Case

Both sides of the case suppressing genuine evidences. Indication present that accused suffered firearm injuries in course of occurrence but prosecution appropriately ignoring to clarify same. Alleged, similarly, failing to settle fire-arm wounds and stab injuries on person of dead. Defense failing to completely institute from its proof its appeal of self-defense. The court thus believed that alleged can still claim advantage of omissions and doubts appearing in prosecution proof such as raise an assumption of presence of a right of self-defense. Fiasco of prosecution to elucidate fire-arm wounds found on person of alleged casting severe doubts on legitimacy of its version. Manner as to how incidence took place and who first started attack not ascertainable.

Conclusion

To conclude the above discussion ,it is crystal clear that the right embodied in self-defense is a sine qua non with rationality , reasonability and utilizations of normal level of discretion to inhibit the hostile acts of others that an individual understand to perpetrated upon

him. The courts at the time of decision may take into concern the situations of the case, the prominent threat to life or goods apprehended by the individual who takes the appeal of right of self-defense and the enormity of the force employed by the accused. Therefore, the burden to prove exercise of this right is upon the accused to prove his innocence. Prosecution will not be meshed to prove case against the accused. The inquiry of such cases shall be acquired with great carefulness and assiduousness so as to preserve the administration of justice. In majority of the conditions, this right is exercised by the local police. The law delivers that when an accused is charge with an crime carries capital punishment i.e. death punishment or life imprisonment and the accused repel his legitimate custody or there is apprehension that he will escape from the legal custody, the local police can use force for his custody and they can utilized it as a lawful reason for their exception if the alleged met death during the course of his custody. However, in most of the time it is termed as extra judicial killings.

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Mahfuz Ullah Arify
Assistant Professor, Faculty of Law and Political Science,
Department of Public Law,
Nangarhar University, Afghanistan
mahfuzullaharify2018@gmail.com

Mohammad Aimal Haqmal
Associate Professor, Faculty of Law and Political Science,
Department of Public Law,
Nangarhar University, Afghanistan
aimal.haqmal@gmail.com

Ahmad Gul Wasiq
Professor, Faculty of Law and Political Science,
Department of Public Law,
Nangarhar University, Afghanistan
ahmadgulwasiq@gmail.com

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